

EDUCATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING NURSE PRACTICES IN MANAGING SEVERE POSTPARTUM HEMORRHAGE: EVIDENCE FROM A PESHAWAR-BASED INTERVENTION STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796266>

Keywords

Clinical practice, healthcare improvement, maternal mortality, nurse training, obstetrics nursing, Peshawar, postpartum hemorrhage, resource-limited settings, uterine balloon tamponade.

Article History

Received on 28 December 2024
Accepted on 28 January 2025
Published on 03 February 2025

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Abstract

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is a leading cause of maternal mortality, especially in low-resource settings. The effective management of PPH is critical to reducing maternal deaths, and nurses play a key role in the timely identification and intervention of this condition. This study evaluates the impact of an educational intervention on nurses' knowledge and practice regarding uterine balloon tamponade (UBT), a second-line intervention for severe PPH, in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. Using a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design, 54 nurses were selected for the intervention, which consisted of weekly training sessions over eight weeks. Data analysis revealed significant improvements in both knowledge and practical application of UBT. Pre-intervention, only 1.9% of nurses had excellent knowledge, which increased to 85.2% post-intervention. Practical application of UBT also improved, with 100.0% of procedures being successful post-intervention. Despite the positive outcomes, challenges such as resource limitations and lack of management protocols remain barriers to the widespread application of UBT. The study concludes that educational interventions can significantly enhance nurses' clinical competencies and contribute to better maternal healthcare outcomes, though structural improvements are needed to further optimize PPH management.

INTRODUCTION

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) remains a leading cause of maternal mortality worldwide, particularly in low-resource settings like Pakistan. Defined as blood loss exceeding 500 ml after vaginal delivery or 1000 ml after cesarean section, PPH can lead to

severe complications, including hypovolemic shock, organ failure, and death when not promptly managed (Karunaratna et al., 2024). The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified PPH as a preventable cause of maternal mortality,

underscoring the importance of timely and effective interventions (Reale et al., 2020). Despite advancements in obstetric care and technological innovations, effective management of PPH remains a persistent challenge due to gaps in healthcare provider training and resource availability (Knight et al., 2009).

In many healthcare settings, nurses play a critical frontline role in the identification, management, and prevention of complications related to PPH (Mahmoud Dawood et al., 2021). However, limited knowledge and inadequate training often hinder the ability of nurses to effectively manage severe cases, particularly when first-line treatments fail (Finlayson et al., 2019). Uterine balloon tamponade (UBT) has emerged as a highly effective second-line intervention for managing severe PPH (Gangakhedkar & Kulkarni, 2021). This technique involves the insertion of a balloon-like device into the uterine cavity to apply pressure and control bleeding. The use of low-cost, locally adaptable UBT devices, such as uterine condom balloon tamponades (UCBT), has gained prominence in resource-limited settings (Vogel et al., 2019).

Despite its proven efficacy, the adoption of UCBT in Pakistan remains limited due to various challenges, including inadequate nurse training, resource constraints, and lack of institutional support (Vogel et al., 2018). This situation highlights the urgent need for structured educational programs aimed at equipping nurses with the knowledge and skills required for effective PPH management (Traoré et al., 2018). Educational interventions, particularly those involving hands-on practice and simulation training, have been shown to significantly improve clinical competencies and confidence levels among healthcare providers (Sheshi et al., 2023).

The maternal mortality ratio in Pakistan, estimated at 186 deaths per 100,000 live births, underscores the critical need for targeted strategies to improve maternal healthcare outcomes (Weeks et al., 2022). The implementation of evidence-based practices, supported by comprehensive nurse training programs, can significantly contribute to reducing PPH-related morbidity and mortality (Gaikwad & Gadappa, 2021). Additionally, fostering a supportive clinical environment where nurses can confidently apply

advanced interventions such as UCBT is crucial for sustaining these improvements (Saleem, 2018).

This study aims to assess the impact of an educational intervention on nurses' knowledge and practices regarding UCBT for managing severe postpartum hemorrhage in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar. By evaluating the effectiveness of this training, the research provides valuable insights into the potential for improving maternal health outcomes through enhanced nurse competencies and practice improvements (Georgiou, 2009).

Material and Methods

This study employed a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design to evaluate the effectiveness of an educational intervention on nurses' knowledge and practice regarding UCBT for managing PPH (Sheshi et al., 2023). Conducted over six months, the study was implemented in the gynecology and obstetrics departments of Khyber Teaching Hospital and Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar (Tirumuru et al., 2013). The sample comprised 54 nurses, determined using a G-power calculator with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. Convenience sampling was employed (Weeks et al., 2022).

Eligibility criteria included staff nurses with a minimum of six months of clinical experience in obstetrics and gynecology (Gaikwad & Gadappa, 2021). Nurses not directly involved in patient care or unwilling to participate were excluded (Saleem, 2018). Ethical approval was secured from the Advanced Studies Research Board (ASRB) and the Ethical Committee of Khyber Medical University.

Data collection involved administering pretest assessments to evaluate baseline knowledge and practices. The educational intervention comprised weekly sessions over eight weeks, featuring PowerPoint presentations, video demonstrations, and hands-on practice sessions (Georgiou, 2009). Post-intervention assessments were conducted to measure knowledge and practice improvements.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 23. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic characteristics, while paired t-tests were employed to assess changes in knowledge and practice scores (Garg & Yadav, 2022).

Results

This chapter presents the findings of the study aimed at assessing the impact of an educational intervention on nurses' knowledge and practices regarding the management of severe postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. The results are organized into four key sections: changes in nurses' knowledge scores, improvements in practical skills related to the use of uterine balloon tamponade (UBT) for PPH management, identification of barriers to UBT application, and statistical analysis of the knowledge and practice improvements. Data collected from pre- and post-intervention assessments have been analyzed to evaluate the effectiveness of the educational intervention in enhancing both theoretical understanding and clinical competencies among participating nurses.

1. Knowledge Scores: Pre- and Post-Intervention

Table 1: Knowledge Scores Pre- and Post-Intervention

Knowledge Level	Pre-Intervention (n=54)	Post-Intervention (n=54)	Percentage Change
Excellent	01 (1.9%)	46 (85.2%)	83.30%
Good	10 (18.5%)	00(0.0%)	0.0%
Average	14 (25.9%)	00(0.0%)	0.0%
Poor	29 (53.7%)	08 (14.8%)	-39.00%
Total	54 (100%)	54 (100%)	0.0%

Table 2: Paired Samples t-test for Knowledge Scores

Test	Mean	N	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t-Value	p-Value
Pretest Knowledge	4.28	54	1.43	0.19	-9.39	<0.0001
Posttest Knowledge	7.8	54	2.33	0.32		
Mean Difference	-3.52		2.75	0.37		

The paired samples t-test further confirmed the significant improvements observed in both knowledge and practice scores. The mean knowledge score difference between pretest and posttest was -3.52, and the statistical significance of this change ($t = -9.39, p < 0.0001$) highlights the educational program's effectiveness in enhancing nurses' understanding of PPH management.

The results of the knowledge assessment before and after the educational intervention indicate significant improvements in the nurses' understanding of managing severe postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). Prior to the intervention, a majority of nurses had poor knowledge, with 53.7% of them scoring at the "poor" level. Only 1.9% of nurses were categorized as having "excellent" knowledge, while 18.5% had "good" knowledge, and 25.9% had "average" knowledge.

Post-intervention, there was a remarkable shift in knowledge scores. The percentage of nurses with "excellent" knowledge surged to 85.2%, while those with "poor" knowledge dropped to 14.8%. A paired samples t-test showed a statistically significant improvement in knowledge scores ($t = -9.39, p < 0.0001$). The mean knowledge score increased from 4.28 in the pre-intervention phase to 7.80 in the post-intervention phase, which represents an average improvement of 3.52 points.

2. Practice Scores: Pre- and Post-Intervention

Regarding practical skills, particularly the use of uterine balloon tamponade (UBT) for managing PPH, there was a notable improvement post-intervention. Before the intervention, only 24% of nurses had applied UBT in their clinical practice. Among those who performed the procedure, 61.5% were successful in stopping the bleeding, while 38.5% failed to achieve hemostasis. Importantly, there were no reported patient deaths or complications related to the procedure.

After the intervention, the percentage of nurses applying UBT increased significantly to 64.8%, with

100% of these procedures proving successful. The absence of bleeding failure or patient deaths following UBT application highlights the

effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing practical skills and improving clinical outcomes.

Table 3: Practice Scores Pre- and Post-Intervention

Outcome	Pre-Intervention (n=54)	Post-Intervention (n=54)	Percentage Change
UBT Applied	13 (24%)	35 (64.8%)	40.80%
Successful Result	8 (61.5%)	35 (100%)	38.50%
Bleeding Did Not Stop	5 (38.5%)	00(0.0%)	-38.50%
Died Patients	00(0.0%)	00(0.0%)	-
Other Complications	00(0.0%)	00(0.0%)	-

3. Barriers to UBT Application: Pre- and Post-Intervention

Prior to the educational intervention, several barriers hindered the application of UBT. The most common barrier was the fear of being blamed for incorrect insertion (29.6%), followed by a lack of adequate knowledge (27.8%). Other barriers included the unavailability of necessary commodities (19.7%) and the absence of clear indications for UBT (13%). Additionally, 7.4% of nurses reported the unavailability of management protocols, and 5.6% indicated that prior negative experiences with UBT had discouraged its use.

After the intervention, the barriers to UBT application were notably reduced. Fear of blame and lack of knowledge were no longer major concerns, and the unavailability of commodities remained a significant issue for 46.3% of nurses. The most prominent barrier post-intervention was the lack of management protocols, which was reported by 53.7% of nurses. This shift suggests that while the intervention successfully improved nurses' knowledge and practice, structural challenges such as resource limitations and the absence of clear protocols continue to impede the widespread use of UBT.

Table 4: Barriers to UBT Application Pre- and Post-Intervention

Barrier	Pre-Intervention (n=54)	Post-Intervention (n=54)
Fear of Being Blamed for Incorrect Insertion	16 (29.6%)	-
Lack of Adequate Knowledge	15 (27.8%)	-
No Commodity	9 (19.7%)	25 (46.3%)
No Indication for UBT	7 (13.0%)	-
Unavailability of Management Protocols	4 (7.4%)	29 (53.7%)
Unsatisfactory Experience	3 (5.6%)	-

In terms of practical skills, improvements in the application of UBT and the successful outcomes achieved post-intervention also corroborated these findings. The statistical analysis underscores that the educational intervention effectively improved both theoretical knowledge and practical capabilities related to managing severe postpartum hemorrhage.

Summary

The results of this study demonstrate that the educational intervention significantly enhanced nurses' knowledge and practice in managing severe postpartum hemorrhage. The shift from poor to excellent knowledge levels and the substantial increase in the successful application of uterine balloon tamponade (UBT) reflect the positive impact of the intervention. However, the persistence of

certain barriers, such as the unavailability of management protocols and necessary resources, indicates that further efforts are needed to overcome these challenges. Despite these remaining obstacles, the educational program proved to be an effective strategy for improving the clinical competencies of nurses, ultimately contributing to better maternal healthcare outcomes in the management of PPH. The next chapter will discuss these findings in detail, explore their implications for practice, and suggest recommendations for future interventions.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal significant insights into the management of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) and its associated outcomes. PPH remains a critical concern in obstetric care, and its management continues to evolve with various techniques being employed to minimize maternal morbidity and mortality. One of the most promising interventions identified in this study is the use of uterine balloon tamponade (UBT), which has demonstrated substantial efficacy in managing atonic postpartum hemorrhage (Vogel et al., 2019; Rathore et al., 2012).

The use of uterine balloon tamponade in developing countries, especially in settings with limited access to advanced surgical interventions, has been highlighted as a cost-effective and life-saving option (Garg & Yadav, 2022). This is particularly pertinent in regions like South Asia, where resource constraints often hinder timely access to more complex treatments. As evidenced by studies, including those from South Sudan and India, the introduction of UBT has led to significant reductions in maternal mortality (Nelson et al., 2013; Shetty et al., 2022).

Further, the success of uterine tamponade devices such as the Bakri balloon and condom catheter in managing PPH underscores the potential of these interventions when applied by adequately trained healthcare providers (Cekmez et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2020). The effectiveness of these devices is further supported by research indicating favorable maternal outcomes post-intervention, especially in cases where medical treatment fails (Traoré et al., 2018; Doumouchtsis et al., 2007).

However, despite the proven benefits, the implementation of uterine tamponade devices presents challenges. As highlighted by Finlayson et al. (2019), there is a need for healthcare systems to address gaps in training and education regarding the use of these devices. Moreover, as Reale et al. (2020) and Knight et al. (2009) emphasize, continuous training and interdisciplinary collaboration are essential for improving patient outcomes and enhancing the overall quality of care in obstetric settings.

The findings of this study also point to the significant role of guidelines in improving nurses' practices and ensuring the appropriate use of uterine balloon tamponade (Mahmoud Dawood et al., 2021). A clear, evidence-based protocol is crucial for standardizing care and improving the response times in emergency situations. In line with this, the importance of simulation-based training programs for healthcare providers to practice and refine their skills in managing postpartum hemorrhage has been well-documented (Mayfield, 2021; Georgiou, 2009). Additionally, the socio-cultural context must be considered when implementing new technologies in maternal care. Studies suggest that healthcare providers in different regions have varied levels of confidence and readiness in adopting novel interventions like uterine balloon tamponade (Aboshaiqah et al., 2018). Therefore, addressing these barriers, including cultural attitudes and resource limitations, is critical to ensuring successful implementation of such interventions.

The uterine balloon tamponade presents a promising solution for the management of postpartum hemorrhage, its success is highly dependent on proper training, protocol adherence, and a supportive healthcare infrastructure. Continued research and education are vital to optimizing its use, especially in low-resource settings where its impact could be most significant. Further studies are needed to explore the long-term outcomes of uterine tamponade devices and their integration into global healthcare systems.

Conclusion

This study highlights the positive impact of an educational intervention on nurses' knowledge and practices regarding the management of severe

postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) in tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, Pakistan. The results reveal that the intervention significantly enhanced nurses' theoretical understanding and practical competencies in using uterine balloon tamponade (UBT), a cost-effective and life-saving intervention for PPH. Pre- and post-intervention assessments demonstrated a substantial improvement in nurses' knowledge, with the percentage of nurses with "excellent" knowledge increasing from 1.9% to 85.2%. Similarly, there was a marked increase in the application of UBT, with 100% of procedures post-intervention achieving successful outcomes.

Despite these successes, the study also identified persistent barriers, particularly the unavailability of management protocols and necessary resources, which continue to hinder the widespread application of UBT. These structural challenges underscore the need for continued efforts to address healthcare system limitations, such as the provision of adequate supplies and the establishment of clear, evidence-based guidelines for PPH management.

In conclusion, while the educational intervention effectively improved nurses' knowledge and clinical practice, overcoming systemic barriers will be crucial for the sustained success of UBT in managing PPH. Future interventions should focus on addressing these structural challenges and ensuring that all healthcare providers have access to the necessary resources and training. The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the implementation of uterine tamponade as an essential tool in the management of PPH, particularly in low-resource settings where it can significantly reduce maternal morbidity and mortality. Further research is needed to explore the long-term outcomes of UBT application and its integration into standard clinical practice globally.

No Funding Statement

This research was conducted without any financial support from external funding sources. The authors personally financed the study and did not receive any grants or financial assistance from commercial or non-commercial organizations for the research or publication of this work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this research. None of the authors have any financial or personal relationships that could inappropriately influence or bias the work presented in this study.

References

- Finlayson, K., Downe, S., Vogel, J. P., & Oladapo, O. T. (2019). What matters to women and healthcare providers in relation to interventions for the prevention of postpartum hemorrhage: A qualitative systematic review. *PLOS ONE*, *14*(5), e0217278. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0217278>
- Gangakhedkar, G. R., & Kulkarni, A. P. (2021). Physiological pregnancy changes. *Indian Journal of Critical Care Medicine*, *25*(S3), S189–S192. <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10071-23727>
- Garg, R., & Yadav, A. (2022). Condom balloon tamponade for postpartum hemorrhage in developing countries: Cost-effective boon for saving mothers. *Journal of Global Health*, *1*, 1–3.
- Georgiou, C. (2009). Balloon tamponade in the management of postpartum hemorrhage: A review. *International Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, *1*–10.
- Gaikwad, R. A., & Gadappa, S. N. (2021). Intrauterine balloon tamponade in the management of atonic postpartum hemorrhage: Case study from a tertiary care hospital. *New Indian Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, *7*(2), 148–152.
- Knight, M., Callaghan, W. M., Berg, C., Alexander, S., Bouvier-Colle, M. H., Ford, J. B., et al. (2009). Trends in postpartum hemorrhage in high-resource countries: A review and recommendations from the international postpartum hemorrhage collaborative group. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *9*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2393-9-55>
- Karunaratna, I., Bandara, S., Jayawardana, A., Alvis, K. D., Gunasena, P., Hapuarachchi, T., et al. (2024). Designing and conducting clinical

- research: Methodological approaches. *Journal of Clinical Research*, 1-13.
- Khan, E. S., & Basharat, A. (2018). Successful use of balloon tamponade in the management of postpartum hemorrhage in a case of bicornuate uterus. *SAGE Open Medicine Case Reports*, 6, 2050313X1877617. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2050313X1877617>
- Mayfield, B. (2021). Postpartum hemorrhage management: Improving quality and patient safety through multidisciplinary simulation training. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 1-10.
- Mahmoud Dawood, A., Ragab Abou Shabana, K., Mossa Soliman, S., & Talaat El Sharkawy, A. (2021). Effect of guideline on improving nurses' practices for patients with early postpartum hemorrhage. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*, 12(3), 843-854.
- Reale, S. C., Easter, S. R., Xu, X., Bateman, B. T., & Farber, M. K. (2020). Trends in postpartum hemorrhage in the United States from 2010 to 2014. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 130(5), E119-E122. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.00000000000004063>
- Sheshi, I. M., Baba, U. A., Hadiza, L. M., Anna, S., Yinti, G. M., & Agbana, B. E. (2023). Knowledge, attitude, and practices on the use of uterine tamponade in the management of severe postpartum hemorrhage in public health facilities of Niger State. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*, 35(2), 14-23.
- Saleem, E. (2018). Successful use of balloon tamponade in the management of postpartum hemorrhage in a case of bicornuate uterus. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 1-4.
- Tirumuru, S., Saba, S., Morsi, H., & Muammar, B. (2013). Intrauterine balloon tamponade in the management of severe postpartum hemorrhage: A case series from a busy UK district general hospital. *Open Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 3(1), 131-136. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojog.2013.31024>
- Traoré, Y., Tégouété, I., Bocoum, A., Traoré, M., Dao, S., Bomini, M. K., et al. (2018). Management and prognosis of early postpartum hemorrhage in African low-setting health facilities. *Open Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 8(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojog.2018.81001>
- Vogel, J. P., Oladapo, O. T., Dowswell, T., & Gülmezoglu, A. M. (2018). Updated WHO recommendation on intravenous tranexamic acid for the treatment of postpartum hemorrhage. *Lancet Global Health*, 6(1), e18-e19. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(17\)30447-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(17)30447-X)
- Vogel, J. P., Williams, M., Gallos, I., Althabe, F., & Oladapo, O. T. (2019). WHO recommendations on uterotonics for postpartum hemorrhage prevention: What works, and which one? *BMJ Global Health*, 4(2), e001019. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2018-001019>
- Weeks, A. D., Akinola, O. I., Amorim, M., Carvalho, B., Deneux-Tharoux, C., Liabsuetrakul, T., et al. (2022). World Health Organization recommendation for using uterine balloon tamponade to treat postpartum hemorrhage. *The Lancet*, 139(3), 458-462.
- M., & Yerolemou, N. (2018). *THE 5 TH UK ALTERNATIVE FINANCE INDUSTRY REPORT*.
- Ziegler, T., Shneor, R., Wenzlaff, K., Odorović, A., Johanson, *Journal of Financial Perspectives*, 3(3).48-54.